

PREPARATION OF STARTING MATERIAL FOR TOMATO SELECTION

Odashev Muhammadusmon Ulug'bek o'g'li

Student of Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10800383>

Abstract

The tomato is native to western South America. Wild versions were small, like cherry tomatoes, and most likely yellow instead of red. The Spanish first showed tomatoes to Europe, where they became used in Spanish and Italian food. The French and northern Europeans wrongly thought that they were poisonous because they are a member of the deadly nightshade family. The leaves and immature fruit contains tomatine, which in large amounts would be toxic. However, the ripe fruit contains no tomatine.

Key words: Breeding, domestication, genomics, *Solanum lycopersicum*

At the end of the 19th century, numerous cultivars of tomato were available in different colours and for different purposes. These cultivars could be considered as landraces and products of domestication and some early breeding. Most of these cultivars require open pollination and the propagation was done by the farmers and growers who could easily obtain seeds from the fruits for the next generation. Because tomatoes do not naturally out-cross very often, seeds of a tomato produce plants resembling the parent. Due to this property, earlier tomato cultivars were selected and inherited in a family or community, thus earning the name heirloom. Heirloom tomato varieties are open-pollinated and are unique in size, shape and colour (Watson, 1996). Available in varieties with diverse characteristics, heirloom tomatoes tend to be prized for their distinctive flavours. At the beginning of the 20th century public institutes, mainly in the USA, became more involved in tomato breeding. Meanwhile, private companies were formed and commercial breeding has shifted open-pollinated cultivars to hybrids. Hybrids combine good characters from both parents that will segregate in the progeny, discouraging seed propagation by growers. The advantages of hybrid varieties over true breeding varieties were so great that the growers would buy hybrid seeds at higher prices. In 1946, the first hybrid tomato cultivar 'Single Cross' was released (Dorst, 1946). Eventually, nearly all tomato cultivars for the fresh market and an increasing number of cultivars using in processing are hybrids.

Although the process of plant breeding is theoretically simple, it does create novelty. The art of tomato breeding is identifying and combining the specific traits for each market. The fresh product is sold in a wide range of shapes and sizes,

from the small cherry tomato to very large beef tomatoes. Typically breeders are continuously improving their breeding lines, either by making new crosses with their own material or by using the cultivars of their competitors, which is allowed by breeders' law (UPOV Breeders Rights, 1961). Breeders in this fashion use naturally occurring recombinations to produce cultivars that combine favourable traits. New traits are rarely introduced from wild germplasm as it may take many generations to remove the deleterious genes that go along with the introduced genes due to linkage drag. When the parental lines are more fixed (F4 to F6), crosses are made to produce test hybrids. After several generations of testing at the breeders' site and eventually at the farmers' sites, the best hybrids are selected for commercial usage. Hybrids of tomato show some heterosis, but this is only selected for at the latest stage of the breeding programme, when test hybrids are generated. In earlier generations the parent lines are selected at a single plant basis but not for combining abilities or heterosis. So, recurrent selection programmes to select parents with the best combining abilities, like that used in field crops, is not a common practice in tomato breeding.

Nowadays, there are a dozen tomato-breeding companies which are the main players in the world market. In order to survive, seed companies must continuously develop new cultivars with added value and hence commercial tomato breeding is very innovative. The average turnover time of commercial tomato cultivars is approx. 5 years. This system results in a very competitive breeding practice and breeding companies can only get return on their investments if they can get high prices for their seeds. This is certainly true for the fresh tomato market, and less so for the tomato-processing industry where seed (and tomato fruit) prices are much lower and the volumes much larger. The annual value of the worldwide tomato seed market is about half a billion euros with the majority being for fresh market tomatoes.

Tomato domestication and breeding: what have we gained and what can we gain in the future?

In this review, we have looked into the domestication and breeding processes in tomato and the new insights from recent developments in tomato genome research. We show that large variation is present and exploitable in the wild *Solanum* species. As a consequence of inbreeding during tomato domestication, the genetic diversity in cultivated tomato is now very narrow. Much of the genetic variation was due to spontaneously occurring mutations that were rapidly introduced into new cultivars if these had added value. Sooner or later, a ceiling of the potential of tomato breeding by only using the cultivated

germplasm will be reached. To explore tomato biodiversity, ILs that carry small introgressed chromosome fragments from related wild species in a cultivated tomato background are most useful. However, it is virtually impossible to exploit all individual wild accessions by generating genetic libraries of ILs, considering >75 000 *Solanum* accessions are conserved in genebanks around the world (Larry and Joanne, 2007). It is expected that in the next decade the genome sequence of tomato, at least for the gene-dense regions, will be determined. With techniques like Eco-tilling, allele mining will greatly facilitate the identification of useful genes in the wild tomato germplasm (Comai et al., 2004). Thanks to the synteny among the Solanaceous crops and even the microsynteny with *Arabidopsis* it is expected that our knowledge about the function of tomato genes will gradually increase. The increasing knowledge from tomato -omics will challenge traditional tomato breeding methodology. With all the genomics, expression and metabolite databases, breeders' capital will shift from the field to the computer. The breeder will select the best combinations of genotypes and design programmes to combine traits in new cultivars in a 'breeding by design' process (Peleman and Van der Voort, 2003).

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Watson B. Taylors guide to heirloom vegetables. New York, NY: Houghton Mifflin Co; 2023.
2. Dorst JCEA (VW) Een en twintigste beschrijvende rassenlijst voor landbouwgewassen. Wageningen, Rijkscommissie voor de samenstelling van de rassenlijst voor landbouwgewassen. 2023:221.
3. Ostonaqulov T.E., Obloqulov D.D. - Takroriy ekin sifatida pomidor o'stirish texnologiyasi. T., 2008.